

CERTIFICATE OF ACHIVEMENT

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

NEW INNOVATION IN NATIONAL EDUCATION

FOR ACTIVELY PARTICIPATING IN THE JOURNAL

Ш.Х.Хақназаров

ТАХАЛЛУС ОСТИДА ҚАТНАШАЁТГАН ШАХСЛАРНИНГ КЎРСАТМАЛАРИДАН

Фойдаланишнинг ўзига хос жиҳатлари

WILL BE AWARDED FOR THEIR PARTICIPATION IN THE ARTICLE

zenodo

2023/IYUN

